

Visual Notes on Maya Glyphs

Christian Prager, 29.03.2021, addenda: 05.04.2021

chuw-k'ahk'-aj „fire-burned“: a new warfare expression

ITN: St. 17

[chu:wV].[K'AK':ja]

ITN: St. 17

[chu:wi].[K'AK':ja]

PRU: HS. 1, XVII

Another argument for T1772 as wu

Polyukhovich 2010: A Contribution to the Decipherment of the **wu** syllable. Unpublished visual note (CHN CM, Lnt. 6; CHN TIS Lnt. 1; YAX Lnt. 10)

☉)))) T285st

Chain of war events

9.17.10.4.14 2 Ix 17 Uo

1

9.17.10.4.15 3 Men 18 Uo

joch' u k'ahk' ihk' ?-ko xook? lakamtuun ajaw juunlat „3 Men“ chuwk'ahk'aj uchan aj pom ch'ak ? tuun u kabjiij uchan k'in bahlam aj ? tuun

Maya Calendar Calculations
Textdatenbank und Wörterbuch des Klassischen Maya
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Correlation Constant: 584285

Long Count	G	Y	Tzolkin	Greg. Date	Jul. Date	Jul. Day	Mayan Day	Moon Age (A)	Moon Age (M)	819
9.17.10.4.14	G4	Y5	2 Ix 17 Uo	6.3.781	2.3.781	2006379	1422094	0.74	2.70	E 313 (15.13)

Drilling fire (during full moon) – Fire-burned – Axing at / of place
(Note: The day Ix is a frequent day for war events)

Etymology

chui „se quemó“ (MOP); *chuiwen* „quemado“ (MOP); *chuwu* „quemaló“ (MOP); *chuw k'aak'* „gusano de fuego“ (MOP); *chuwik* „quemar“ (MOP); *chuij* (ITZ); *chuw* „to burn“ (pYu)

chuw-k'ahk'-aj uchan aj pom „he fire-burned, uchan aj pom“ (intransitive compound expression)

Acknowledgements

The identification of the *wu* decipherment goes back to David Stuart, who also considered the reading *hu* for this sign. David Stuart and Stephen Houston (29.03.2021) drew my attention to the occurrence on Hieroglyphic Staircase 1 from El Perú, where the possible *wu* character is replaced by *wi*. The occurrence must be verified by a photograph.